

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable

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NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighboring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Abstract

The present document describes the general methodological framework to be utilized for the assessment of NEANIAS' business perspectives and innovation cases. To achieve this task, several methodologies are being employed that enable the identification and detailed description of the external and internal factors that can potentially influence the NEANIAS ecosystem. More specifically, the market analysis deconstructs the economic environment that NEANIAS is expected to be a part of, drawing useful conclusions about the existent economic forces. Then, the business modelling looks to further understand the NEANIAS services and its surroundings, understanding how they can interconnect with each other, a foundational part of the analysis that can enable sustainability through the provision of invaluable information. All gathered intelligence regarding the services and the market is leveraged by the technoeconomic model that translates detailed information into numerical values, particularly monetary ones. These can be directly used for the evaluation of the project's sustainability, regarding business perspectives through market analysis, business modelling, technoeconomic analysis, and cost-benefit analysis for each service for providing internal feedback to service providers. The aforementioned methodological steps are described in detail in the following sections followed by a general overview of how they will be brought together to provide fruitful results. Furthermore, the described methodology can enhance the value derived from the EOSC ecosystem, while easing the difficulties in the integration for Neanias and similar future initiatives.

1. Introduction

The evaluation of innovative services, at the early stage of development is generally a very challenging process, as the risks behind development and the possible utilization areas are most of the time not clearly described. The services of NEANIAS are at the moment in the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 6, and is expected to reach TRL8. TRL6 means, that the technology is demonstrated in relevant environment, which should be later tested in operational environment (TRL7), in order to achieve TRL8, when the system is complete and qualified.

NEANIAS is targeting this challenge, and the services developed in the frame of NEANIAS undergo the procedure of testing and evaluation by involving the end-users, described in WP5, and by developing and implementing business cases. Therefore, the principles of open innovation are taken into consideration when interactive value production with the involvement of the end-users in the development process is taking place. This co-creation mechanism is supplemented by the evaluation of business perspectives through market analysis, business modelling, technoeconomic analysis, and cost-benefit analysis for each service.

The aim of this analysis is to create a financially sustainable service offering in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem. “The EOSC should be a federation of existing and planned research data infrastructures, adding a soft overlay to connect them and making them operate as one seamless European research data infrastructure.” [1] The EOSC ecosystem therefore provides the innovation and application net in a complex networked-based system, that researchers and end-users can use to develop sustainable services.

NEANIAS aims to uncover the potential of the business cases and seeks to identify the key elements and the opportunities that are currently hidden in the booming era of innovation and open (research) data identified by modern EU and international studies. These opportunities are to be explored within the context of the EOSC portal where NEANIAS services are to be made available. The EOSC portal is a marketplace for researchers and professionals, offering data and services related to science, technology, the humanities and social sciences. One of NEANIAS’ goals is to exploit this e-hub and make itself visible and accessible to all possible interested stakeholders. It comes as a logical and promising approach to incorporate the possibilities that are brought forward by EOSC into the general sustainability plan charted for the NEANIAS project.

All these evaluation methodologies will be aligned to specific industries and the thematic sectors. The evaluation methodologies described in this deliverable are general, and their elements can be modified and specified to the attributes of each service.

This deliverable details the market analysis to be implemented in the frame of 2.1, with specific attention on the market entry barriers, market segments, pricing, competition and regulations. There are additional tools, like strategic posture, scenario planning and stakeholder analysis described, which can be used to evaluate the specifications of each thematic service.

The influencing factors of business modelling are described in section 2.2, to introduce the methodology when evaluating the services and define the main steps in sustainability. All this relates to describing the main frame for planning the utilization of NEANIAS thematic services.

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Sections 2.3 and 2.4 are focusing on the Techno-economic and Cost benefit analyses. In general, the NEANIAS consortium aims to explore the opportunities and the models of sustainability of the service exploitation, which will be summarized in the frame of a business plan, including clear “go” or “no-go” decisions on the services. This decision is supported by the methodologies described in this deliverable.

2. Methodologies

In this chapter necessary market analyses and forecasting tools will be discussed together with a detailed methodology on how to build a successful business model for a product, with a focus on software products. Although this methodology has been designed to support the commercialization process of the NEANIAS services, it can also be used to help other software-based services meant for EOSC integration.

2.1. Market analysis

Market analysis is the collective term of all activities exploring conditions that have an effect on the product or the marketplace it is meant to be positioned in. Market analysis is important to show investors that enough knowledge has been gathered and that the market size is sufficient enough to build a sustainable business model. The main elements every market analysis should have are: demographics and segmentation; target market; market need; competition; barriers to entry; and regulations.

2.1.1. Main Elements of a Market Analysis

The main elements of analyzing the market is briefly mentioned in this paragraph. The market analysis of each service will follow mostly the same structure; however, it will be defined with special characteristics. Each service and thematic sector is different; therefore, their market can be analyzed with individual approach. The services might be specified to target a well-defined market need, or the targeted users might be limited to one definite end-user group. In the following, it is key to mention the key elements of a market analysis:

a) Demographics and Segmentation

Demographic segmentation characterizes and divide the market into smaller groups, and can refer to all features such as age, gender, location, interest, income, occupation, ethnicity and religion, family structure; in general, to a definite group of people, who are relevant with regard the service.

b) Target Market

Target market refers to the group of (end) users from a specific area, that are targeted with the product, and probably might utilize and purchase it. The size of the target market refers to the total number of individuals or businesses, who can be a potential customer/ end-user of the developed technologies.

c) Market Need

Market need analysis identifies what the customers (target market) desires. This can be the improvement of an existing product or even a completely new one. By defining the market need, the real problem of the user is defined, for which the service is providing a solution. The relevance of the problem is also identified, with the possible solutions for them.

d) Competition

Competition is generally defined as a rivalry between companies or products, which aim to solve the same or similar customer pain or satisfy the same market need. Realistically, these companies have similar resources and objectives to compete within the landscape.

e) Barriers to Entry

Barriers to entry refers to the obstacles a company has to overcome in order to become a player in any given industry. There are several market entry barriers, depending on the service, among others like resource ownership, patents and copyrights, government restrictions; the cost of starting up a new venture, brand identity, customer loyalty, high customer switching costs, licenses. There might be further market entry barriers, depending on the specifications of the service. In general, the higher the barrier to entry, the larger the competitive advantage is for existing players.

f) Regulations

Rules and regulations are a set of government restrictions and laws in order to keep businesses running in a certain way or prohibiting them to act unethically/ harming the overall economy.

2.1.2. Recommended Additional Tools

In addition to the above mentioned, it is advised to complete the first analysis with some additional frameworks, because of the nature of the NEANIAS projects. Emerging technologies might be subject to more uncertainty because they have not yet been tested in real-life and their intended use cases can change rapidly together with the market they have been designed for. In order, to get ahead of the end of the life-cycle curve, it is highly advised to complete the following analyses as well: Strategic Posture & a Portfolio of actions; Scenario Planning; Opportunity Analysis; and a Stakeholder Analysis.

2.1.2.1. Strategic Posture

Strategic posture [2] was designed to complete a strategy in highly uncertain, volatile futures. Emerging technologies belong to this category, because they have not yet been tested in real-life situations and are competing with a number of other possible inventions, which can potentially solve the same problems. Strategic posture refers to how the companies wishes to position themselves in the present and in the future within the industry. The three types of strategic postures are: *shapers, adapters, and the ones reserving the right to play* (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The three strategic postures [2]

Shapers change the direction an industry is going towards, they are “shaping it” to their terms. They redefine how every player in the given field should be structured, they choose the mainstream way to go towards. It is possible to do so by either shaking up an existing, stable industry or by trying to grasp the leadership role in more unstable markets.

Adapters are the industry players who build their strategy based on the current industry and take its characteristics as a given. This type of strategic positioning requires advanced level of recognition and response to market changes dictated by shapers.

Reserving the right to play mainly applies for companies with any sort of competitive advantage that will keep them in a superior position compared to other industry participants. This is possible through strategic alliances for example.

By finding the right strategic posture for the developed technologies both in the present and forecasting it correctly in the future can help companies identifying their risks and prepare for them in advance. Depending on the postures, there are different risk factors, and areas to analyse. The best way to analyze the future and get ahead of unexpected events is through scenario planning.

2.1.2.2. Scenario Planning

Scenario Planning [3] can help a company prepare for future uncertainty and therefore prepare for unexpected events. By successfully adapting the scenario matrix the developers can forecast how the technologies will be used in the future and prepare features to keep them relevant and useful even in times of high uncertainty. One of the most helpful tools for scenario planning is the Scenario Planning Matrix (figure 2), this matrix contains two types of uncertainties that can happen in ten or twenty years from now, however are not very likely at the moment. These uncertainties are usually chosen from a list of uncertainties collected in advance through brainstorming and ranked in order depending which one is the least unlikely scenario. Then each uncertainty’s two opposing outcome is assigned to the two ends of the arrows. For example, Figure 2 prepares the positioning of the service in the case of high-low cost of technology development and available-unavailable skilled workforce. Then asks the company to describe the way their business model would look like in case these two

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constraints come true. Scenario planning can help forecast possible outcomes, especially in industries where competitive volatility is high.

Figure 2: Scenario Planning Matrix [3]

Competitive volatility [4] refers to the uncertainty of the behavior and strategy of other market players. One type of competitive volatility is convergence, when another type of product feature will be adapted to satisfy the same market need in different ways.

2.1.2.3. Stakeholder Analysis

A stakeholder refers to any person or group of people, who express interest or concern regarding a business or in this case, the emerging technology.

The “Stakeholder Onion” (Figure 3) [5] is one of the most common ways to gather and analyze all stakeholders. It usually consists of three main parts:

- Internal Stakeholders (e.g.: employees, managers, developer)
- Direct External Stakeholders (e.g.: suppliers, creditors, shareholders)
- Indirect Stakeholders (e.g. government entities, the media)

Figure 3: Stakeholder Mapping [5]

It is important to conduct a stakeholder analysis and keep it up-to-date, as they can have both negative or positive effects on the technology and its usage. By monitoring these stakeholders and their interest, a great deal of issues can be solved beforehand and can help sustain the technological advancement.

2.2. Business modelling

“Business model” is a widely used term, even though there is no definition that is concluding or generally accepted. Originally, the term was defined by Peter Drucker in the 50's, who started the debate about business models in the management science with the “logic of business” [6]. Timmers [7], *for example*, employs a very general idea of the term. In his perspective, the business model describes the product and gives a definition of the various stakeholders attached to the company. Additionally, the business model requires an explanation of the benefits for those different business actors and for the company employing the product. For Timmers [7], a business model also has to add the possible sources of revenues. Wirtz [8] describes the business model as the business approach and the consequences for everyday business. A comprehensive overview and comparison of various business model approaches can be found in [9], as well as in [6].

2.2.1. Business Model Canvas

Within the many different approaches and definitions, the “Business Model Canvas” developed by Osterwalder and Pigneur [10], is a meaningful way to show the business model in a structured and comprehensive way, and can be used as a blueprint to define business strategies for enterprises. Osterwalder and Pigneur define a business model as “the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value”. For this purpose, there are predefined building blocks for the main specifications of a company, which cover the most important aspects of its business model.

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Figure 4: Business model canvas [10]

Figure 4 shows an overview of this business model and its main nine (-9-) building blocks. The overview is a visual representation of how these blocks are interrelated, within the business model.

The business model canvas can be split into three major groups of building blocks: The right part is the customer group (customer relationships, customer segments, channels), the left part focuses on resources of a business model (key activities, key partners, key resources). Underlying to the business model is the financial structure with revenue streams and costs. A central aspect is the value proposition, which defines what a business model is built around. Table 1 gives brief definitions for each of the nine building blocks.

Table 1: Building blocks of the canvas model [10]

Building Blocks	Explanation
Value Propositions	Package of products and services, which provides added value to the customer segment.
Customer Segment	Defines the group of people or organizations, which the company wants to address.
Channels	How to reach, acquire and foster customers.
Customer Relationship	The way a company interacts with its different customer segments.
Revenue Streams	Generated income from different customer segments.
Key Resources	Necessary resources needed in order to create a working business model.

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Key Activities	Most important tasks being undertaken for a business model to work.
Key Partners	The network of suppliers and partners, which enable the success of a business model.
Cost Structure	Costs, which arise during the execution of a business model

2.2.1.1. Value Proposition

The Value Proposition describes the product and service bundle that creates value for a specific customer segment. It solves a customer problem or satisfies a need in a way that gives customers a reason to choose a company's product over another. The value proposition is the basis for all other building blocks and strategic aspects of the business model, and it can have entirely different specifications and design options. It comprises of the following concepts:

- **Product Innovation:** Addresses new needs that the customer was not aware of, because there was no comparable product before.
- **Improved Performance:** The improvement of a product or service is a well-known method of value creation.
- **Customization:** Tailoring a product to the specific needs of a specific customer or segment creates value.
- **Design** is an important factor but difficult to measure. A product can be superior to competitors', because of its design.
- **Brand/Status:** Many customers find value in the brand or status of a product they are using.
- **Ease at Work:** The product helps the customers to make their business easier.
- **Price:** Offering a valuable product with a lower price is a common method to serve the needs of a price-conscious customer segment.
- **Cost/Risk Reduction:** An important method for creating value is to help the customer to reduce their costs or risk.
- **Accessibility:** Making products and services available to customers who had previously no access to them creates substantial value.
- **User Friendliness:** Making things more convenient to use can create substantial value.

2.2.1.2. Customer Segments

The customers are invariably in the center of the value creation process of a successful business model. The Customer Segments building block identifies the different groups or entities that an enterprise may intend to reach. It is vital for every business model that a conscious decision is made about which customer groups to attend and which to ignore. We consider the following markets:

- **Mass market:** The mass market focus, basically makes no distinction between different customer segments. Value proposition, distribution channels and customer relationships are aimed at all types of consumers with similar needs and problems.

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- **Niche market:** Business models that focus on a niche market have specific and specialized customer segments. The other building blocks of the business model necessarily follow the particular needs of the niche market.
- **Segmented:** In a segmented approach, a business model distinguishes between customer groups with different preferences and problems. Again, this differentiation has consequences for all building blocks of the business model.
- **Diversified:** The diversified customer segment approaches serve two customer segments at once that are not directly related to each other. These customer groups have different preferences and demands.
- **Multi-sided platforms:** Finally, businesses can serve two or more customer segments that depend on each other. All segments are necessary to make the business model work. Providers of credit cards or free newspaper are good examples for multi-sided platforms.

2.2.1.3. Channels

The Channels in a business model can be understood as the company's "interface" with their customers. They comprise the means of communication, distribution and sales with and to their customers. Channels are the points of contact with the customers and, *therefore*, play a very important role for the customer experience.

For these purposes, there are different direct and indirect channel types that can be provided by the business promoter or a partner, as shown in Figure 5:

Figure 5: Direct and indirect channel types

2.2.1.4. Customer Relationships

The Customer Relationships building block describes the different styles of relationships to be established with the various customer segments considered, in order to engage them to the product.

Those relationships can range from very personal to automated and follow different motivations, such as customer acquisition, retention or increasing sales via upselling.

Figure 6: Types of customer relationships

2.2.1.5. Revenue Streams

Revenue Streams define the amounts of funds and the ways in which a company receives these funds from its customers in exchange for its products or services.

The crucial question each business model must answer is which value is generated by a product for which the customer is truly willing to pay for. From there, a business model can lay out one or several revenue streams from each segment of customers.

These revenue streams can be differentiated along two lines:

- Revenues resulting from one-time customer transactions.
- Constant, recurring revenues from sequential – such as monthly – payments to continue delivering a value proposition to the customer or to provide post-purchase support.

Table 2: Types of revenue streams [10]

Revenue stream	Description
Subscription	In a <i>subscription model</i> , the customer exchanges a recurring service delivery or constant access to a service for continuous payments.
Item-based	In an <i>item-based revenue model</i> , an asset/service is sold by the company to its customers. Thereby, the ownership rights to a physical product are transferred to the customer.

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Advertising	In an <i>advertising model</i> , a business offers space or an advertising slot to its customers, where they can generate awareness or reputation for their own product.
License	The <i>licensing model</i> permits the customer to use a protected intellectual property in exchange for a fee. Licensing is common in the media industry (copyrights) and in the technological sector (patents).
Leasing	In a <i>leasing model</i> , a company grants someone the exclusive right to use a product for a predefined period of time. The customer can use the product, but has to return it at the end of the leasing period.
Commission	The <i>commission-based model</i> builds upon providing an intermediation service between two or more parties. In exchange, the provider of these services earns a commission fee.
Cross-subsidization	When a company has a <i>cross-subsidization revenue model</i> , it does not get the money from the actual customer but from a third party. Usually, the revenue stream from cross-subsidization comes from a player that has an interest in the company for providing a product or a service.
Usage fee	In a <i>usage fee model</i> , often in the form of a pay per use-model, the revenue is based on the frequency and extent the service is used by the customer.

2.2.1.6. Key Resources

Key Resources are the most important assets that make possible a specific business model to work.

The Key Resources are specific to the business model and are used by the enterprise to create and offer its value proposition. They can be physical, financial, intellectual, or human in nature.

Furthermore, a company can own, lease, or acquire those resources from contractors.

- *Physical*: Such as production facilities, vehicles and distribution infrastructure
- *Intellectual*: Resources like brands, know-how, patents, copyright and development partnership.
- *Human*: In knowledge-intensive or creative industries, business models rely heavily on human resources
- *Financial*: Such as cash, a line of credit, or a stock option pool for hiring key employees.

2.2.1.7. Key Activities

The building block of Key Activities describes the most important actions a company must take to make its business model work.

Just as on the resource side, Key Activities are needed to create and offer value to customers and may differ depending on the type of business model.

We consider the following concepts:

- Production includes the design, manufacturing and delivering of products.
- Consulting meant to solve the problems of individual customers. Generally, this requires extensive human resources (well-trained workers and know-how).
- Platform/Network Administration running and maintaining a technical platform that provides services to its customers. It also implicates for gathering and clustering of a certain group of people with similar interests or needs in a network.
- Platform/Network Development Refining and enhancing the features of a technical platform or network, according to the evolving needs of its users/the network's members.

2.2.1.8. Key Partners

The building block of Key Partnerships describes the network of suppliers and partners that are contributing to the value creation of a business.

There are numerous reasons why companies start partnerships, such as strategic alliances between non-competitors, joint ventures, or buyer-supplier relationships to assure reliable supplies.

There are two fundamental types of partnerships: Exclusive and Non-Exclusive. In an exclusive partnership, a business is bound to another firm for a specific resource or service, whereas in a non-exclusive partnership, a business can have several partners for the same resource.

2.2.1.9. Cost Structure

The building block of Cost Structure refers to the costs that an enterprise incurs when running its business model.

Creating and delivering value, maintaining customer relations and collecting revenues are all drivers of a business models' costs. The incurred costs can be deducted from the Key Resources, Activities, and Partnerships of a business.

We distinguish the following options regarding costs:

- Fixed Costs: Fixed costs are costs that remain the same, despite changing volumes of goods and services produced (e.g. building rental).
- Variable Costs: Variable costs are costs that change proportionally with the volume produced (e.g. purchase of goods for production).
- Economies of Scale: Moreover, economies of scale are cost advantages that a business enjoys as its output increases. These can be due to discounts on large quantities of supplies bought or an enhanced degree of capacity utilization.

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- Economies of Scope: Economies of scope are cost advantages that a business enjoys, due to an increasing scope of operations, related mainly synergies between the production and distribution channels of multiple products.

2.2.2.77 Business Case Definition

The following Figure 8 showcases how to involve the end-users in the technology developing process. It includes innovations manager(s) as well, who’s role is to foster clear communication and keep the activities going towards the right outcome.

Figure 8: How to involve end-users when creating the business model

The first step as shown on Figure 8 is to clearly define the service and its features and to define the business problem it should solve. Once, the service developers have done this they can now deliver the service with its user instructions to the end-users. The service now will need to be tried out and reviewed, based on these reviews, it can either be accepted or rejected (and be sent back to the developers). If the service solves the business problem defined in the beginning, the innovation manager(s) will help define the competitive advantage it will give the end-users. If it is not solving the problem of the end-users on an acceptable level, it is going to be sent back to the developers for further review. Service developers then modify services and send the service over again for trying out by the end-users. Once it is on a satisfactory level, innovation manager(s) help to finalize the service and prepare it for wider commercialization.

2.2.3. Business model innovation

While it is important to compose the business model successfully, it is equally important to shape it throughout time to the changing environment. There are four areas one has to take into consideration when innovating the business model (Figure 9). Such influencing factors include cognitive, environmental, relationship, and managerial areas.

Figure 9: Business Model Innovation Influencing Factors [12]

The *cognitive* part aims to shift the traditional perception of the business model and implement new approaches, such as the network-based business model. To do so all industry players will need to shift their logic from the traditional linear models and abandon best practices from the past. The model will need to be shaped to the product, while it is itself is being tested and changed throughout an ongoing process. Lastly, the business model will need to point towards the long-term strategy. The *relationship* part refers to the alignment between business partners and industry players. Co-creation and open innovation are concepts that can help foster such collaboration. The *environmental* part needs to be considered when evaluating the changing eco-system and the players in it. This change refers to anything that affects how the end-product gets delivered to the end-users. The *managerial* part covers all elements involving flexibility. The business model's elements need to be modular and flexible, the importance of this is so that small changes do not cause the entire business model to collapse.

Supporting concepts to help the business model innovation will be introduced in the following chapters.

2.2.4. Network-based business model

2.2.4.1. Overview

Network-based business development is the most suitable option when exploiting novel technology-based services. "Network" in this context means that all the processes involve a diverse range of actors from both the supply and the demand side. This happens in order to get the most out of the services, their development, production and commercialization. Furthermore, it is crucial for the above-mentioned players to coordinate and combine their activities throughout the whole development process. In order to do so, the concept of co-creation is advised to be adapted. Co-creation is important so that the technology and the business model designed to exploit it could integrate the needs of the industry.

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Figure 10: Figure Network Based Business model development [13]

Figure 10 showcases the process of network-based business model development. When it is very different from the traditional processes as it includes many trials while finalizing the business model. Because the model is being shaped around the changes made throughout the process, companies can save a lot of unnecessary expenses of having to change fundamental elements at the end. The framework involves three phases: *R&D Phase, Implementation Phase and Market Phase* and collects the type of networks, whom are essential for the complex development of each one, including the milestones the company has to achieve under them. The EOSC ecosystem provides a complex base for research partners and end-users. In Figure 10, it positions as the innovation and application net. By developing the base services to align with the EOSC infrastructure, both developer partners and customers can leverage the previously collected knowledge, allowing them to sustain the heritage of Neanias.

2.2.4.2. The EOSC Concept

The European Open Science Cloud has been created so that the stakeholders of the European science community can leverage the existing data infrastructure and sustain it by building on it. By adding more and more functionality to the structure, the EOSC ecosystem has the potential of becoming a global leader in research data management and open up to a wider user base. The strategy of the EOSC ecosystem builds towards an open science model, that can be implemented both on a union and on a national level [1]. The use of the network-based business development model complements this initiative by helping researchers and end-users create the most fitting commercialization strategy, further enhancing the complexity of the ecosystem.

2.2.4.3. The network perspective

The “network perspective” [13] on one hand refers to the company’s position in the network, on the other hand all other players who help forming it. By creating the business model

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considering third party actors, the value created through its services can be truly maximized, in addition to new market opportunities and reduced expenses. The service developer might not be able to explore all application areas of its service or acquire all skills to do so, this is where the importance of the network lies.

Figure 11: Possible business opportunity creation through the European Open Science Platform

As we can see from Figure 11, by integrating a platform where knowledge of the developed services can be openly shared, the number of business models created increases exponentially, hence increases the number of successful outcomes as well. It has been observed that companies engaging actively in open innovation, manage to harvest more value from their own technologies as well.

2.2.4.4. Opportunities

By identifying the business opportunities first, the foundation of the business model and its commercialization can be built. For technology-based services it is even more necessary to explore as many opportunities as possible, since their development and commercialization strategy is yet to be planned [13]. Opportunities in a network-based business development refer to both integrating the technologies into existing business models, or by creating spin-off companies, generating additional entrepreneurial ones as well. The network-based business model builds on this opportunity and encourages players to find additional user areas for the developed technologies.

2.2.4.5. Challenges

Developing network-based business strategies for novel technologies is a relatively new concept, therefore, one of the key challenges [13] is the lack of studies and literature on the topic. Gathering existing frameworks and guidelines will help overcome the academic obstacle and focus on the more complex issues to be tackled.

The first such obstacle is **trust** between the network participants. Trust is described as “the single most important element when building business networks” [13]. This can be achieved by clear and on-going communication both within the organization and between network players by adapting a communication strategy from the very beginning. The second challenge of a well-orchestrated network is **complexity**. It is crucial to involve a diverse range of activities and resources. This will enhance the quality of the output of the networks. Third challenge to overcome is **knowledge management**. Knowledge should flow between the networks, so that the most value could be harvested from this complex cooperation. Last, but not least **leadership** can either challenge or add value to these networks. Leadership should keep shaping the strategy so that it fully aligns with the networks.

2.3. Techno-economic analysis

The general goal of the technoeconomic analysis is to examine all NEANIAS services, to accurately evaluate and assess their potential and viability in terms of economic value. To do so, the first step is to identify all costs that need to be incurred in order to design, create, make available and maintain the relevant services. Then follows the estimation of expected revenue streams which alongside the results of the costing process provide the necessary insights to understand the long-term economic characteristics of a service. Comparing costs against possible revenues using a technoeconomic model allows for the selection of appropriate business plans and pricing strategies to achieve the goals set by NEANIAS on a business level.

An overall description of the required tasks and how these are interconnected is illustrated in Figure 12. The overall objective is to make an estimation of all expenses and revenues associated with each of the NEANIAS services for a time period starting upon the end of the project (study period). The blue color represents initial inputs that must be used for the analysis, while the orange represents intermediate calculations that are performed based on the previous assumptions. The green color is used for Revenues and costs that are classified into Capital Expenditures (CAPEX) and Operational Expenditures (OPEX). Finally, the red color represents the results. The following section describes briefly what each of these boxes represents:

- Demand estimation: a model that estimates the adoption for each NEANIAS service
- Usage requirements: expected usage of resources required by the users
- Activities: list with all activities that are necessary for offering the service
- Platform architecture: identification of all the hardware related assets that are necessary for the provision of the service
- Assets unit price: the cost of the hardware components and their evolution over time
- Service tariffs: the amount of money that each service is charging the users
- Other: includes parameters used for the financial calculations such as study period, discount rate, tax rate etc.
- Number of users: this as a calculation of the actual number of users of each service based on the total number of potential users and the demand model
- Usage: expected usage of the platform by the users
- Activity based costing: costs driven by the activities
- Revenues: calculation of Revenues based on the number of subscribers and the service tariffs

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- OPEX: all required Operational Expenditures to offer the service
- CAPEX: all required Capital Expenditures to offer the service

Figure 12: Techno-economic analysis

The techno-economic analysis can be analyzed in the following steps:

- 1. Define services and products.** The services / products to be provided must be defined and specified by their owners/creators. This procedure of enumerating and describing those services is performed by the service providers, and yields a handful of estimations, requirements and possibilities that are required for estimating the revenues and costs of the overall offering of the project. It is essential that this procedure yields the characteristics of each service/product that define the potential customer target group for each of them (i.e. where potential users/customers can be drawn from).
- 2. Define study period.** Initially the duration of the study period is defined. The study period for each of the NEANIAS services will be defined at a later stage as it depends from the characteristics of each service. As a general guideline, a four to six-year period is reasonable, considering the time it usually takes services to reach market maturity and provide at least one major update of the provided solution, which is essential in order to consider the full product/services lifecycle in the analysis. In similar projects related with software development a rule of thumb is that every three to four years the products need a major update.
- 3. Business model input.** For each of the use cases a preferred business model that describes the stakeholders and interactions with them is defined. This is a critical step

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in the methodology in which all ecosystem stakeholders must be identified. The interaction between them describes the potential revenue sources and helps identify drivers of costs related to the platform's operation.

- 4. Market and revenue definition.** In this step, the revenue sources are defined, and their amount is estimated together with the service owners. For each service/product several parameters need to be defined such as the market penetration forecast over the study period and service tariff amongst others. Service demand significantly impacts system dimensioning and, as a consequence, both system / infrastructure and service cost. In order to forecast service demand, potential users of the services such as government agencies, research networks, industry etc. will be defined. The number of users of existing data and services will be investigated and will be the input to specialized models describing the diffusion process of their life cycle.

The combination of market penetration and service tariff estimates, returns the revenues per year for each of the service sets. Due to the nature of the products and services, other funding sources must be also considered as options if required to ensure the financial sustainability of the endeavor, while other forms of "value" of the services may be considered.

- 5. Definition of resource requirements and system dimensioning.** Service providers define the dimensioning rules while the analyst attaches pricing and price forecast rules. The result of this procedure is the so-called "shopping list" which is directly used to forecast the required infrastructure in order to provide the defined services. This list outlines the volumes of all infrastructure cost elements, type of resources (virtual and physical) along with reference costs and price forecasts for each of those resources.

The aim of system dimensioning is to estimate the required resources such as HW and SW components (PCs, servers, links, licenses, etc.) to implement the suggested solution. The dimensioning process estimates the use of sub-components (such as CPUs, memory etc.) that are required in order to satisfy the technical requirements and provide the necessary services.

The main parameters that are used in system dimensioning can be divided into two categories:

- Technical parameters
- Market-related parameters (demand forecast).

Since the results of system dimensioning will significantly affect the reliability and initial cost of deployment, each parameter used in the dimensioning process should be examined in depth.

- 6. Identification of the operating expenses.** A full list of the costs required for the provision of various services (such as office rental, marketing, salaries, support, IPR purchases etc.) and estimation of their size, is assembled by service providers and the analyst.
- 7. Simulation of the proposed scenarios.** All the aforementioned factors are inserted into a model that is used for the execution of various analyses and extraction of KPIs such as Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR) etc. that help identify the financial viability of the proposed solution. Furthermore, sensitivity and risk

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analysis are performed in selected variables in order to identify their contribution to the KPIs.

The difference between traditional “plain” sensitivity analysis and risk analysis based on Monte Carlo simulation is that the former only reveals what is *possible*; not what is *probable*. In traditional sensitivity analysis, a number of variables are selected for the study and they are altered one at a time to measure their individual impact on the final output. Often, what-if scenarios are constructed with different combinations of worst-case, base-case and best-case values of each of the variables. Monte Carlo simulation, however, makes it possible not only to assign a probability distribution to each variable (we know that some variables are more uncertain than others) but also to update all the selected variables automatically and simultaneously. Random numbers are generated according to the selected distributions for each of the selected variables for the risk analysis. The simulation therefore calculates a large number (the number of simulation trials is specified by the user) of what-if scenarios. What is more, Monte Carlo simulation also allows us to keep track of the calculations for every change in each variable by measuring their individual impact on the final output. The type of probability distribution assigned to the variables under investigation is based on the variable’s statistical properties.

The next sections present an overview of the existing methodologies for cost estimation that can be used in NEANIAS. The decision on which of the methodologies will be used will depend on the data that will be available for each of the services.

2.3.1. Cost modelling

Cost modelling is a vital part of the assessment of the business side of NEANIAS, along with the clear goal of achieving the highest possible level of precision in calculating all relevant costs that arise with the creation of the project’s services. In order to calculate the cost of providing the NEANIAS services it is necessary to design and implement a framework in which all related costs are identified, quantified and allocated using the appropriate cost driver that characterise the services. The cost modelling process includes the following steps:

- Identify expenses: in this step all the expenses are identified
- Identify cost drivers: the driver for each of the identified expenses is determined
- Dimensioning rules: in this step rules between cost drivers and expenses are created

Several cost models have been developed that use estimations, algorithms, or parametric equations to calculate the costs of products and services. We can classify them into the following categories.

2.3.1.1. Estimation based on analogy

Estimation based on analogy is a method of estimating costs by utilizing information drawn from similar past projects. The similarity comparisons are drawn based on a set of independent attributes that are evaluated in order to identify projects that are closely related to the one that is being evaluated. The selection of the attributes is dependent on the available information while various methods for calculating attribute proximity, e.g. Euclidean distance, machine learning, fuzzy logic and others have been proposed [32]. Effort values of the most

similar projects are used to produce estimates for the effort needed for the target project, i.e. the one that is being examined.

2.3.1.2. Expert judgement

One of the traditionally and heavily used techniques of cost estimation that leans on knowledge and experience instead of the utilization of past data to support the evaluation of costs. This approach can prove especially useful when there is lack of data and a degree of specialization is present that relates to experts' know-how. Limitations on available information can create an environment that favours expert judgement instead of computational techniques allowing for more accurate results even though it might seem counter intuitive. Expert knowledge may not be always parameterized by an algorithmic model, making expert judgement the better option to internalize aspects of product development [33]. But there are also disadvantages, as experts can prove to be susceptible to biases and overestimation [34]. One example of an expert judgement methodology is the well-known and documented in the literature Delphi technique.

2.3.1.3. Top-down modelling

This technique calculates the total cost using either algorithmic or non-algorithmic methods and then allocates it to the various components that comprise the studied system. It is more effective when historical data are limited and subsequently becomes suitable for cost estimation at early developmental stages [35]. Being efficient in costing activities such as integration and management it is differentiated from other techniques in that regard, but is less capable when considering low level cost drivers that may exist that influence costs [36].

2.3.1.4. Bottom-up modelling

Following the opposite approach of the top-down method, each component of the system is separately estimated, and the aggregated results produce the cost of the overall system. To perform this type of cost modelling the initial design needs to be existent to be able to compose a complete and informed model that accurately estimates costs [35]. Constructing a model that is built from the ground up, considering all possible system components can provide a specificity and stability that other more high-level approaches cannot, but at the same time it may lack their insightfulness, missing out on costs factors such as documentation, integration and others [36].

2.3.2. Cost methodologies

In this section, the most common methodologies are described. The methodologies to be used for the purposes of NEANIAS will be decided based on use case basis and information availability.

2.3.2.1. Activity based costing

Activity-based costing (ABC) emerged in [17] as an alternative method to traditional cost accounting methodologies. It aims to identify activities, related cost drivers and then allocate costs to the products that make use of these activities. Thus, there is established a two-step process that identifies actions and how they are performed allowing the cost calculation of a company's services. ABC has been employed in several fields such as manufacturing [18], digital preservation [19], healthcare [20] or even in a more general context as in [21], [22] that consider the benefits that ABC can offer to small companies or projects, enabling accurate

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product cost understanding. One of those benefits is the ability to create better distinctions between activities that adhere to more than one product, for example management which often overlooks multiple products.

The ability to dissolve possible fuzziness on activities that are part of multiple processes of product development is anticipated to help with the accurate costing of NEANIAS' services. This is particularly important when the development of a service includes several activities that might differ in nature and would possibly need to be split up into developmental subtasks. One such example could be data procurement in comparison to algorithm development. Within the context of a technoeconomic model, these two activities need to be separated, but may be performed by the same person in an organization. Considering only the aggregate Full-time Equivalents (FTEs) spent by the employee for these two tasks, does not portray an accurate picture of the cost structure of an organization. Additionally, as also stated in [INC 6], traditional costing systems were more suitable to broad production environments while ABC proves more agile when variety is present, another characteristic that is closely relevant to the NEANIAS project as a whole.

Apart from the applicability of this methodology in particular situations, its value as a way to understand costs and improve efficiency in various setups is being studied by the scientific community as seen in several publications [23], [24], [25], [26]. Underlined is the ability to achieve higher levels of accuracy in cost allocating and the provision of information that allow better understanding and management of resources. Additionally, a structured approach of describing activities is provided by ABC that further improves the way services and products are being perceived in economical as well as managerial terms. Based on the conclusions drawn by the literature, ABC is anticipated to play a strong role in aiding the NEANIAS consortium to comprehend and analyse the actions that shall take place to develop the proposed services as well as the costs that are associated to them. Moreover, one major advantage that ABC has over other costing methodologies is the ability to efficiently identify indirect costs that are incurred during the development of a product [27]. Detailed cost analysis subsequently provides valuable input to product pricing decisions and aid in establishing a robust business plan solidifying prospects of sustainability for the future.

The implementation of the ABC methodology follows a sequence of steps as in [28], starting from the identification and definition of the activities and elements of cost within an organization while establishing the relation that exists between them. As a result of this initial process, the development of a product or service can be analysed in the activities that need to take place and their respective costs. By associating activities performed to cost objects (i.e. products, services), a connection is created between products, activities, and costs. The following Figure 13 further clarifies the described methodological steps.

Figure 13: ABC methodology diagram

Once the relations between cost drivers, activities and cost objects have been described, they can be expressed in more mathematicised terms within a technoeconomic model used to accurately calculate product costs by utilizing actual cost data gathered. For example, the development of a software product would most certainly require software developing activities, that are cost driven by the working hours that developers need to dedicate to the process. The number of working hours multiplied by the hourly rate of the employees would produce the costs incurred for this activity. Performing this calculation for all identified activities leads to particularly realistic cost calculations. The benefit of utilizing a technoeconomic model is its ability to provide dynamic characteristics to the calculations. Altering the numerical relations between activities and cost drivers or even creating new connections based on the organizational structure adopted is a possibility that provides adaptability. Thus, an appropriately designed model can be utilized for various products, an attribute that matches well with NEANIAS project where multiple services that share similarities are being developed.

One of the difficulties that characterizes ABC is that often the same activity can be performed several times but with varied intensity, demanding for some sort of alternative description of the same activity. By incorporating time spent and hourly rates into the implementation of the methodology, this main drawback is alleviated [29], further enhancing the suitability of ABC for NEANIAS' needs as flexibility could prove to be essential in enabling a cost model that brings together the services that are being developed.

2.3.2.2. Cost models for data handling

Having discussed the framework and principles that characterize the ABC methodology, it is then beneficial to reach a greater level of analysis by listing the possible activities and cost components that the technoeconomic model may include. Previous work has been conducted on this subject providing consolidated knowledge that can be leveraged for the purposes of NEANIAS. One notable example is the 4C¹ EU funded project that performed a thorough study

¹ Collaboration to Clarify the Costs of Curation

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of available models for the curation of data. The studied models utilize identified activities to accurately calculate costs and possible benefits data related services. In [30], these models and all the relevant information they utilize to accurately calculate costs are discussed, including activities, variables and resources. The activities related to data curation are depicted in the following Table 3.

Table 3: List of activities

Activities
Production
Pre-ingest
Ingest
Archival Storage
Data Management
Administration
Management
Preservation Planning
Access

Based on the OAIS reference model in [31], the activities are separated into internal and external operations that are part of the general process of data handling.

The internal activities are the following:

- *Ingest* refers to the services and functions to accept the digital content
- *Archival Storage* refers to the services and functions for the storage, maintenance, and retrieval of the digital content
- *Data Management* refers to the services and functions for populating, maintaining, and accessing information which identified and documents content in the Archive as well as administrative data used to manage the archive
- *Administration* refers to services and functions for the overall operation of the Archive
- *Preservation planning* refers to the services and functions for monitoring the environment of the Archive, providing recommendations and preservation plans to ensure the digital content remains accessible
- *Access* refers to the services and functions that support consumers determine the existence, description, location, and availability of the digital content stored in the Archive allowing consumers to request and receive information

The external activities are the following:

- *Production* refers to the process of providing the information to be preserved
- *Management* refers to the process of setting the overall policy followed by the organization that handles the digital content

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These activities are not necessarily present in all cases of data curation as is observed in the 4C costing models review previously referenced and that is expected to be the case for the NEANIAS project. Nonetheless, it is useful to establish all those activities that are potentially part of the development of the NEANIAS services and provide solid groundwork to utilize as a starting point.

Apart from the activities, [30] also examines variables and resources that are just as important in modelling the costs of services. The following Table 4 shows a collection of resources utilized by other models.

Table 4: List of resources

Resources
Capital cost
Operational cost
Labor cost
Fixed cost
Variable cost
Source lines of code
Direct costs
Indirect costs
Outsourcing
Total cost
One-time cost
Term cost
Annual cost

Most of the resources depicted in the previous table are commonly used in cost models and deal with specific types of costs that are incurred during the development of a product.

- *Capital costs* are fixed, one-time expenses that may include, for example, the purchase of building space, equipment, materials etc. *Operational costs* are the recurring costs such as energy, internet access, space rental, wages etc.
- *Labor costs* are the employees' wages which scale depending on role and are also affected by the economic environment surrounding an organization.
- *Fixed costs* are those that remain constant regardless of changes in the production process in contrast to *variable costs* that change. Space rental is considered a fixed cost, even though it may situationally change but cloud infrastructure costs may vary depending on the amount of data handled or the processing power needed to complete certain tasks, two conditions that change depending on changes in demand.
- *Source lines of code* is a resource/metric that can be utilized to evaluate the potential labor required to complete a software development project and subsequently quantify the expected incurred costs.

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- *Direct* and *indirect* costs are a way to categorize costs in respect to them being attributable to the product development. Indirect costs are not easily allocated in comparison to direct costs, but important to be depicted if a cost model is to provide accurate cost calculations. Cloud computing resource are easy to allocate to a process in contrast to power consumption that can be influenced by other activities, for example the development of an unrelated product.
- *Outsourcing* is a possible solution in cases where need for external expertise can prove to be more efficient than trying to produce results from scratch.
- *Total costs* are used by some models that empirically evaluate the aggregated costs of activities, an approach that may provide useful information but lacks analytical perspective.
- *One-time, term, and annual costs* refer to the time related classification of costs.

The resources expected to be identified for the services of NEANIAS are expected to fall into these discussed categories, a process that helps in the detailed manipulation of data gathered in a uniform way. Indicative examples that fall into each category have been described to enhance the understanding of the resources that should be taken into consideration by the cost model. That will also help avoid misrepresentation of costs and bring greater detail in the construction of the cost model.

Table 5: List of variables

Variables		
Migration frequency	Types of items	Volume per assets per year
Number of assets	Organization site	Type of storage system
Capital Cost	Collection levels	Number of copies of information asset
Labour salaries	Preservation aims	Person-hours per week
System purchase costs	Number of depositors	Accommodation
Commercial software licence	Number, mode, frequency of deposits	Linear depreciation of capital
Archive media	Number, complexity, type of file formats	Keys for distributing indirect costs
Inflation	Metadata quality	Hardware
Volume	Complexity	Corruption rates
Automation level	Type of personnel	Half-life for cost
Retention period	Quality standards applied	Access costs
Number of items	Types of information assets	FTE day rates

The variables listed in Table 5 are the parameters that are specific to the products modelled and fall into the general resource categories. They affect the final cost and are subject to dimensioning rules as is defined by the technoeconomic model. For example, a commercial

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software license is paid for per person as is usually the case in SaaS pricing schemes as would be for hardware purchases, e.g. laptops. The goal is to understand the forces that drive each variable and its costs, aiming to construct a structured mathematical way to adjust variables based the specific needs of the final product. For example, estimating the number of workers needed to complete the product development in time does not only allow the calculation of labor costs but also the precise evaluation of several other related cost elements such as, hardware, software, office materials requirements etc.

2.3.2.3. Cost model for software development

2.3.2.3.1. Constructive cost model (COCOMO)

A popular and much utilized algorithmic model more known as COCOMO, capable of evaluating software costs through the usage of parameters and estimations from previous projects for calibration purposes. Through the years various versions of the model have been developed in order to cover different needs but all of these versions follow the same seven-step methodology depicted in Table 6 described in [37].

Table 6: COCOMO methodological steps

Step	Description
1	Analyse existing literature
2	Perform behaviour analysis
3	Determine form of model and identify relative significance of parameters
4	Perform expert judgement/Delphi assessment
5	Gather project data
6	Determine Bayesian A-Posteriori update
7	Gather more data, refine model

Regarding Step 4 of this methodology, it can involve multiple rounds of Delphi survey if needed, allowing to capture experts' beliefs on what influences development effort. Step 5 deals with data collecting in order to confirm the cost-estimation relations that are included in the model, a process more easily conducted if there exists data availability. Step 6 combines project data with the expert judgement utilizing statistical techniques aiming to balance data from previous projects and expert analysis.

The general mathematical form that COCOMO uses, per [37], is the following:

$$PM = A * \left(\sum Size\right)^{\sum B} * \prod (EM)$$

where,

PM = person months

A = calibration factor

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Size = measure(s) of functional size of a software module that has an additive effect on software development effort

B = scale factor(s) that has an exponential or nonlinear effect on software development effort

EM = effort multipliers that influence software development effort

The distinction between additive, exponential or multiplicative comes from the nature of the factor that is studied. Consider the effect that an additional software module has on development effort compared to a newly identified service requirement. In the first case, a local addition is introduced while on the second case more drastic changes might need to take place for the whole project to adhere to the new requirement. This is a simple explanation that shows the difference between what constitutes an additive factor compared to an exponential or multiplicative one. During the lifecycle of the COCOMO software solution several high-level types of cost factors have been identified and are part of the evaluation process as shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Cost factors utilized in COCOMO [35]

Type	Cost Factors
Product factors	Required reliability; product complexity; database size used; required reusability; documentation match to life cycle needs;
Computer factors	Execution time constraint; main storage constraint; computer turnaround constraints; platform volatility;
Personnel factors	Analyst capability; application experience; programming capability; platform experience; language and tool experience; personnel continuity;
Project factors	Multisite development; use of software tool; required development schedule;

Depending on the organization or a project’s nature this list might differ, but the general methodological approach holds in how the cost is calculated as the COCOMO model is flexible enough to accommodate differences in modelling needs.

Based on these cost factors and utilizing the model’s mathematical equation, one can estimate the effort needed, compliant to the degree of complexity that rules the specific factors that were previously described. The following Table 8 shows how these factors can range in impact within the cost model based on the degree of the complexity that characterizes an activity.

Table 8: Cost factors and weights in COCOMO [35]

Description	Rating				
	Very low	Low	Nominal	High	Very high
Product					

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Required software reliability	0.75	0.88	1.00	1.15	1.40
Database size	-	0.94	1.00	1.08	1.16
Product complexity	0.70	0.85	1.00	1.15	1.30
Computer					
Execution time constraint	-	-	1.00	1.11	1.30
Main storage constraint	-	-	1.00	1.06	1.21
Virtual machine volatility	-	0.87	1.00	1.15	1.30
Computer turnaround time	-	0.87	1.00	1.07	1.15
Personnel					
Analyst capability	1.46	1.19	1.00	0.86	0.71
Application experience	1.29	1.13	1.00	0.91	0.82
Programmer capability	1.42	1.17	1.00	0.86	0.70
Virtual machine experience	1.21	1.10	1.00	0.90	-
Language experience	1.14	1.07	1.00	0.95	-
Project					
Modern programming practice	1.24	1.10	1.00	0.91	0.82
Software tools	1.24	1.10	1.00	0.91	0.83
Development schedule	1.23	1.08	1.00	1.04	1.10

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These factors and their weights multiplied constitute the multiplicative part of the initial equation previously shown in this section that essentially calculates the effort *EM*.

Likewise, a similar procedure can be followed to calibrate the *Size* part of the equation through the usage of the scale factors *Bi*. These behave similarly to the cost factors and are shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Software scale drivers in COCOMO [35]

Software scale drivers
Precedentedness
Development flexibility
Architecture/Risk resolution
Team cohesion
Process maturity

The most important attribute of the methodological approach adopted by COCOMO is the ability to consider various inputs (i.e. cost drivers and software scaling drivers) that characterize the development process and then adjust the model to the needs of the specific project discussed. Thus, it allows to reduce uncertainty when estimating the associated costs while simultaneously allowing to perform risk assessments on the numerical values used and provide a more complete picture of the possible cost profile of a project.

2.3.2.3.2. *Function point analysis*

Function point analysis is a methodological approach that seeks to estimate software size by categorizing software requirements and then assessing them on grounds of complexity. As described in [38], function points constitute a weighted sum of the number of inputs, outputs, master files, and inquiries provided to or generated by the software. The identified function points are assigned complexity levels ranging from 1 to 3 (1 = simple, 2 = medium, 3 = complex) and weights varying from 3 (simple input) to 15 (complex internal files). The unadjusted function-point counts (UFC) is derived utilizing the following equation:

$$UFC = \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^3 N_{ij} W_{ij}$$

where, N_{ij} and W_{ij} are the number and weight of types of class i with complexity j as explained in [35]. For example, for a project consisting of two simple inputs ($W_{ij} = 3$), two complex outputs ($W_{ij} = 7$), and a complex internal file ($W_{ij} = 15$). Then the equation would calculate as $UFC = 2 * 3 + 2 * 7 + 1 * 15 = 35$.

The UFC results can be used as is or modified to produce other numerical factors such as estimates for lines of code (LOC) using the following:

$$LOC = a * UFC + b$$

The parameters a , b can be estimated utilizing historical data or other algorithmic ways such as regression analysis.

A substantial degree of correlation between function points and eventual SLOC as well as the work effort required to develop the code have been shown to hold as stated in [38], rendering the methodology a valuable tool in software cost assessment. This method is not depending on a specific programming language or tool, allowing it to be applicable to a broad spectrum of projects. On the other hand, it requires a great understanding of the work that is expected to be completed to accurately define the function points and quantify the complexities that characterize them.

2.3.2.3.3. *Putnam's model*

This model functions by analysing numerous previous projects and the distribution of manpower during their development. Constructing a connection between size and effort, it provides a formula for calculating software costs utilizing the following equation:

$$S = E * Effort^{1/3} * t_d^{4/3}$$

where,

S = the size of the software in lines of code,

E = the environmental factor depicting development capability,

t_d = software delivery time,

$Effort$ = the effort represented in person year

The effort can be further represented through the following equation:

$$Effort = D_0 * t_d^3$$

with D_0 representing manpower build up, ranging from 8 for entirely new software to 27 for rebuilt software. An advantage of Putnam's model is its reliance on only two variables, namely time and size but this advantage comes along with a related drawback and an inability to take into consideration varied aspects of software development [36]. The Putnam model is being used for the estimation of cost and manpower scheduling by software solutions such as SLIM.

2.3.2.3.4. *Estimating lines of code*

Lines of code (LOC) is the number of functional lines of source code and is commonly used to express software size and related to cost in most methodologies. Accurate estimation of the LOC needed is not an easy task, as is the case in general for the cost estimation of software development. Regardless, techniques have been developed to estimate code size to be used in tandem with expert judgement. One such technique is PERT that utilizes three expert code-size estimations, lowest possible size S_l , highest possible size S_h , and the most likely size S_m . The estimate is derived using the following equation

$$S = \frac{S_l + S_m + 4 * S_m}{6}$$

This approach can be employed for individual software components enabling more targeted estimations which are then summed up to derive the total LOC projected for the entirety of a project.

2.3.3. Revenue Modelling

Revenue modelling is critical part of the technoeconomic model with high participation on the overall evaluation of the project. The goal is to estimate the expected revenues that the developed services can generate and to do so there are some factors that need to be carefully considered. The estimation of demand is of particular interest as it understandably plays the most crucial role in defining and calculating revenues for a model. Essentially, having the ability to perform a prediction on the number of consumers that will utilize a service is what enables revenue estimation. Additionally, products or services can be influenced by a growing number of consumers and may need to allocate additional resources to be able to accommodate additional demand.

Estimating demand is a challenging task in its own right, as data availability on consumption trends heavily defines the methodologies to be used to conduct forecasts. Of course, if such data is indeed available, standard forecasting techniques can be used (e.g. logistic functions, regression, neural network etc.) but issues arise when no information is available. Since NEANIAS services are brand new, no historical data will be present, but comparisons could be drawn to other similar products to adopt trendlines that can be adjusted to different levels of intensity. These will depend on the market characteristics that are identified on earlier stages of the project's assessment. In practice that would mean including into the model a share that NEANIAS is expected to carve out of the market based on how organization that offer similar services perform. Additional information that can help quantify potential demand for the services can be drawn from economic growth data of the relevant markets, historical data of publications utilizing software or algorithmic solutions that are enhanced by NEANIAS or bear similarities, the utilization of conclusions drawn from the market analysis conducted as described in this document, etc.

Having a time-series that expresses expected demand is then utilized to calculate revenues based on identified ways of monetisation in the business modelling part of the project analysis. The pricing schemes can be compared against each other (e.g. subscription vs licence) to make decisions based on profitability which will depend on consumer demand, nonetheless. Exploration of revenue possibilities is obviously an integral part of the sustainability assessment of NEANIAS and one should consider the capabilities provided by the EOSC platform, the nature of such a platform and the benefits that come along with its characteristics. It could affect the way revenues are generated and NEANIAS services visibility subsequently placing it at least under consideration in regard of modelling perspective.

2.4. Cost-benefit analysis

To perform a well-rounded evaluation of the NEANIAS project and the ways it can positively impact relevant stakeholders, a cost-benefit analysis (CBA) is to be conducted. In broad terms,

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a cost-benefit analysis is a systematic effort of identifying impacts, categorized as benefits and costs, and their subsequent quantification aiming to determine the net benefits of the examined projects, meaning the benefits minus the costs.

$$NetBenefit = Benefits - Costs$$

It becomes easy to observe the need to accurately quantify benefits and costs in order to be able to solve a mathematical equation in a CBA context. As a result, great focus needs to be placed in the methodological approach that defines those two foundational parts of the calculations. But, apart from a well-defined benefit/cost quantification, there also lies great importance in the thorough identification of possible stakeholders, not limited to the directly involved organization. The attention placed onto the understanding of the multifaceted character of the project studied renders CBA into a useful tool for gathering necessary understanding and knowledge that further enhances the ability to assess and ameliorate.

The analysis in the scope of NEANIAS, as dictated by project timings, is conducted ex-ante and as such will be able to provide positive and actionable feedback on the development of the project [38]. This ability is tightly related to one of the goals set for this deliverable, i.e. the ability to include feedback loop features that shall help NEANIAS partners consider non-technical aspects of technology assessment, ensuring the sustainability of the proposed system.

According to [39], to simplify the CBA methodology it is useful to separate it into nine, distinguishable steps as depicted in the following Table 10.

Table 10: Cost-benefit analysis methodological steps

Step	Description
1	Specify the set of alternative projects
2	Decide whose benefits and costs count
3	Identify the impact categories, catalogue them, and select measurement indicators
4	Predict the impacts quantitatively over the life of the project
5	Monetize (attach monetary values to) all impacts
6	Discount benefits and costs to obtain present values
7	Compute the net present value of each alternative
8	Perform sensitivity analysis
9	Make a recommendation

These are general methodological steps that should be adjusted, if needed, to suit the characteristics of the project that is being evaluated. Taking a closer look into the steps allows for a preliminary understanding of how the methodology can be adopted relative to the needs of NEANIAS.

1. *Specify the set of alternatives*

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In this first step the idea is to draw comparisons between the project that is being evaluated against alternative routes that could be taken, resembling in perspective the assessment of the opportunity cost that lies behind the development of the evaluated project. In the case discussed in this document, the NEANIAS services are to be compared to the *status quo*, meaning to state before any new services were developed.

2. *Decide whose benefits and costs count*

This step considers the benefits and costs that are related to the project examined, answering the question on which streams of cost and benefits are relevant as there is the possibility that broad scale impact should be discussed. In the case of NEANIAS a substantial number of potential end-users have been identified (Table 11) in early development stages, that provide useful guidelines for the completion of this methodological step.

Table 11: NEANIAS services end-users

Underwater	Atmospheric	Space	Core
Archaeologists	Urban air quality authorities	Astrophysics scientists	All NEANIAS user services
Geologists, Biologists, Oceanographers, Environmental Scientists	Geologists	Planetary scientists	Users of EOSC core services
Oil & gas engineers	Geohazards, civil protection	Planetary mining engineers	Developers of EOSC core services
Renewable energy planners	Meteorological services	Planetary robotics	
Robotics	Energy and power sector and industrial air pollutant emitters	Computer vision, machine learning software engineers	
Civil engineering	Ecologists	Mobile telecommunications	
Computer vision, machine learning software engineers	Rural, urban planners	Space weather	
Insurance	Insurance, health		

These possible beneficiaries could also be grouped up in categories if it is considered suitable. Accordingly, all costs that are incurred to provide the NEANIAS services shall be included as calculated by the technoeconomic model as described in previous sections.

3. *Identify the impact categories, catalogue them, and select measurement indicators*

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The term impact is broadly used to include inputs and outputs as the concept is to identify the ways that stakeholders are impacted. For example, NEANIAS expects to greatly aid its end-users to minimize time spent when performing various related to its services tasks, minimizing the costs incurred. Potentially, every cost category identified in the cost modelling section of the technoeconomic analysis can be also considered as an impact category in the CBA analysis. In this step it is also examined if second level relationships arise such as research spillovers for example. Also, impact measurement indicators are also defined, e.g. FTEs when less time is spent on tasks that are now covered by NEANIAS services.

4. *Predict the impacts quantitatively over the life of the project*

The project is evaluated over a long time period and the CBA should be accordingly conducted to consider its long-term costs and benefits. Predictions over demand, resources needed to serve the expected demand, costs associated with maintenance, data provisioning etc., are all extending into the future and affect the long-term sustainability of the project.

5. *Monetize (attach monetary values to) all impacts*

The impacts identified in the previous step are expressed in monetary value based on the measurement indicators attached to them. For example, FTEs are utilized in tandem with wage rates in order to calculate the costs associated with employee costs incurred for the services to be developed and maintained. Each impact category is treated and estimated separately.

6. *Discount benefits and costs to obtain present values*

As a project is estimated for its impact into the future, this step calculates the aggregated benefits in present values, this being a more tangible way to assess the monetary values calculated. For a project with a study period of n years and discount rate s , a value x in year t is converted to its present value utilizing the following equation:

$$PV(x) = \sum_{t=0}^n \frac{B_t}{(1+s)^t}$$

7. *Compute the net present value of each alternative*

The net present value (NPV) for each alternative is calculated using the following:

$$NPV = PV(B) - PV(C)$$

The alternative with the highest NPV is to be selected as the most appropriate option while in the NEANIAS case, where comparisons are drawn against the status quo, a positive NPV is the driver of the evaluation, meaning benefits that exceed the costs.

8. *Perform sensitivity analysis*

There exist elements of the CBA that introduce uncertainty into the methodology, such as the predictions regarding the future impact, which are inherently unstable as is true in greater or lesser degree for forecasts in general. To alleviate these issues a sensitivity analysis is performed on parameters of the analysis that carry the most uncertainty. Sensitivity analysis is discussed in more detail in section 2.3 and the

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simulation techniques that are utilized to uncover how probabilistic study of the technoeconomic model can provide useful insights.

9. *Make a recommendation*

Based on the analysis that is performed on all previously described steps, the evaluation is concluded providing quantitative feedback that can be used to estimate the project's impact and its sustainability.

Apart from the general methodological steps discussed that were contextualized according to NEANIAS needs, there also exist other aspects that may influence the CBA. One important attribute of the services to be developed by NEANIAS as well as the data gathered is their compliance to the principles of FAIR. It has been shown that there are sizeable benefits in being FAIR as [36] shows. Avoiding overlapping spending on similar activities can lead to unnecessary sunk costs as [37] discusses something that can be the result of several factors such as time spent, storage costs, duplicate funding and more. The beneficiaries of NEANIAS should be able to avoid incurring such costs, by utilizing the available services and databases rather than reinventing the wheel. The costs modelled in the technoeconomic model should be rather straightforward to calculate and incorporate within the cost-benefit analysis. Thus, understanding the special attributes of the evaluated project is also an important part of the CBA analysis that can help perform a realistic examination that is targeted and as such can expect to be more accurate.

3. Overall methodology

The methodologies discussed in the previous sections possess stand-alone value and can draw useful conclusions independently. But, there also exists a great degree of complementarity and this is something that should be leveraged in order to reach a broader understanding and level of analysis within the general scope of sustainability assessment. Commencing from a higher-level perspective, following a stepwise approach, accumulating and leveraging knowledge on the forces that influence NEANIAS services will enable the sustainability assessment as a whole and its ability to be detailed and accurate.

Analysing the market comes in play as a step that identifies the ecosystem that surrounds NEANIAS and is an invaluable process as it allows to achieve foundational understanding of the markets that the developed services are going to be a part of. This has theoretical as well as practical benefits, since later stages of the sustainability assessment, for example the cost and revenue modelling, share a reliance on market understanding to achieve overall accuracy. Essentially, every identified characteristic within the context of the market analysis has the potential to influence the project's assessment and thus holds value for the analysis conducted in general.

Following this perspective, business modelling provides additional analytical capabilities as depicted through the utilization of the popular "*Business Model Canvas*" technique. Several pieces of information coming from the market analysis are incorporated into the canvas which provides a detailed depiction of the processes and interactions that lie behind the development of value from an organization. Consisting of building blocks such as cost structure, revenue streams, resources etc, information can be leveraged in next methodological steps, establishing a close relation between the qualitative and quantitative examination of the NEANIAS services.

3.1. Suitable Business Model for Space, Atmosphere and Underwater Technologies

There are many different combinations of existing business models depending on the nature of the company and the landscape it aims to compete in. There is no better or worse business model, the applied one will depend on the nature of the business. As shown on Figure 7 the recommended model for NEANIAS services, among others is cloud-based, open source, using licensing as a revenue stream, uses "many-to-many" interaction.

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Figure 7: Business model element recommendations for NEANIAS services [10]

As described on Figure 7 above, the business model can be defined by several characteristics, which can be different for each project. The characteristics can be extended or exchanged with several other features, in align with the specifications of the projects, for which the business model is created. This model above describes the main elements and approach when creating a business model.

Thus, it can be observed that most, if not all, elements of the market analysis and business modelling methodologies become important aspects of the technoeconomic analysis. To create a concise technoeconomic model, attention to detail is certainly required as well as a continued effort to include all economic parameters that are identified as building blocks of the product modelling. For example, to define the costs incurred for the development of a product all key resources utilized are taken into consideration to calculate the aggregate service cost.

3.2. Sustainable Business Model Development for Neanias Services

The general approach within NEANIAS is to evaluate the business cases one-by-one, define the industry specifications and set up business models accordingly. The main elements of evaluating sustainability are the following, which can be done parallel:

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Figure 8: Next steps with milestones

The order of these elements is flexible, these steps can be conducted parallel, in align with the industry specifications.

In the frame of WP5 – Business Innovation Cases, each thematic service will be tried out and developed by the involvement of the end-users. The development of the thematic services will be done by using the feedback of the end-users on the service specifications. The details of co-creation are elaborated in the frame of matchmaking events, where the service developers and the end-users agree on the details, including milestones, KPIs, attributes of testing, deadlines, etc. These matchmaking events are already taking place in the frame of WP5, therefore interactive value creation with the involvement of the end-users started. Innomine, responsible for coordinating that WP is providing its expertise on identifying further areas of utilisation. The results of WP5 will be used in WP9, in Business Modelling and Sustainability Analysis, and innovation onboarding.

To summarize, the methodologies described in this document are expected to be utilized in tandem to answer the question posed by the objective of this document, i.e. the assessment of NEANIAS services and their long-term sustainability. Regarding cost modelling, it is important to note that not all methodologies are necessarily employed. Instead, depending on received data and information and based on suitability, different methods may be applied on a case by case basis. What is presented is a general methodological framework capable to adapt to needs that may arise, considering the varied services that comprise the NEANIAS ecosystem. What is expected to be produced is a clear and detailed depiction of all characteristics that describe and define the developed services from a business perspective. That includes both internal and external ones as it is instrumental to understand not only what is being produced but also the ecosystem that it will become a part of. The ability to understand the economic environment of the services becomes increasingly important in the context of eInfrastructures and the forward looking approach that should be adopted to be in sync with trending technological advancements that directly influence business perspectives and needs. Then, the detailed description of the economic attributes is to be utilized in order to produce tangible in the form of monetary values results, representing those modelling components that are expected to be part of a technoeconomic analysis, i.e. costs and

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revenues extending into the future for the duration of the projects prospected lifetime. The expression of the project in monetary values is also to be used by the cost benefit analysis that shall provide exploitable results for the evaluation of the NEANIAS services in its entirety.

4. Conclusions – Future Steps

The methodology will ultimately depend on the models and policies adopted by the EOSC platform. For this reason, we will closely monitor the activities of EOSC in order to be able to understand how NEANIAS may be influenced and how it can fully exploit the cloud platform's capabilities. Particular points of interest coming out of EOSC's sustainability plan [41] are the following:

- differences in the legal and policy requirements for freely available and payment-based services are expected
- the cost of operating the services will not be included in the EOSC-Core funding model
- services made available via EOSC-Exchange may be available free of charge or against payment
- EOSC-Exchange will not be involved in the transaction

Also, possible incentives for service providers are discussed with a main focus being placed on:

- an EC funded means to compensate publicly funded service providers for the additional operational costs they incur.
- a centrally organised and aggregated procurement activity is undertaken by EOSC and funded by the EC (commercial service providers)

All the referenced points are to be examined during the implementation of the methodologies described in this document, as they will pose influence unto NEANIAS, being characteristics of the hosting platform that NEANIAS aims to be a part of.

The first step is to define the tools that will be used and create the initial business models aligned to the characteristics of the services of NEANIAS thematic areas that will be reported in D9.3 (M18). At the next step the market analysis will be performed, the appropriate revenue and cost model that will be used for each service will be defined. These will be the inputs of the techno-economic analysis that will be presented in D9.5 (M32). The results of the cost benefit analysis will be presented in D9.4 (M34). Finally, D9.6 will present the final outcomes for the sustainability of NEANIAS services. The roadmap for the sustainability activities of WP9 are illustrated in the following figure.

NEANIAS Sustainability Roadmap

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
ABC	Activity based costing
SLOC	Source lines of code
LOC	Lines of code
COCOMO	Constructive cost model
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable
FTE	Full time equivalent